

IMPLEMENTING THE DIGITAL PRODUCT PASSPORT IN THE EEE SECTOR: DRIVERS, BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract	<p>This document provides the anonymous and summarised results of a survey conducted among the members of the CIRPASS-2 Expert Working Group 4 'Electronics Stakeholders Group' (EWG4) on the drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges related to the Digital Product Passport (DPP) for Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE).</p> <p>The survey represents a focused update of a deliverable produced under the CIRPASS project, with a specific emphasis on the EEE sector. Its aim is to build on previous insights while capturing sector-specific needs and perspectives.</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS & ACRONYMS

DPP - Digital Product Passport

EEE – Electrical and Electronic Equipment

ESPR – Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation

EU – European Union

EV – Electric Vehicle

EWG4 – Expert Working Group 4

FMD – Full Material Declaration

ICT – Information and Communication Technology

IT – Information Technology

SME – Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

1 INTRODUCTION

Introducing the Digital Product Passport (DPP) in the European Union (EU) is an important step towards accelerating the transition to a circular economy, boosting transparency and compliance, and fostering the environmental sustainability of various economic sectors. DPPs are envisioned as a central source of product data to support the circular economy in many economic sectors across multiple actors and processes. Examples of such data include product composition, environmental footprint, instructions for repair or disassembly, and end-of-life management. Collecting and sharing such data may help bridge the information gap that currently prevents the efficient adoption of circular practices and business models.

DPPs are the object of ongoing legislative work, with the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), the Battery Regulation, and the related delegated acts by sector at the forefront. Depending on the sector, the development of the DPP comes with uncertainty regarding its requirements and effects. The target sector of this document is the Electrical and Electronic Equipment (EEE).

This document provides the summarised results of an anonymous survey that was held among the members of CIRPASS-2 EWG4 on drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges for the implementation of DPPs in the EEE sector. The main difference between the four elements of the survey lies on their temporal dimension: drivers and barriers refer to current dynamics, while opportunities and challenges envision future situations. Drivers and barriers support or hinder the implementation of DPPs. Opportunities and challenges are favourable circumstances and potential dangers, respectively, expected to emerge from the future use and application of the DPP. This work is an update of a previous study, conducted in the context of the CIRPASS project, by adding an explicit focus on EEE to take into account the sector's specific characteristics.

The document is structured into four main parts. Section 2 briefly presents the previous study conducted in the CIRPASS project. Section 3 describes the current survey and the results obtained when focusing on the implementation of the DPP for EEE. Section 4 portrays additional feedback from the Expert Working Group 4 'Electronics Stakeholders Group' (EWG4) and section 5 provides conclusions.

2 PREVIOUS STUDY ON DRIVERS, BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND CHALLENGES

The survey proposed to EWG4 was based on the following study realised in the context of the CIRPASS project:

- Alcayaga, A., Berg, H., Hoffmann, N., Brüggmann, H., Maus, F. (2024). The Digital Product Passport (DPP) for the Circular Economy: Recommendations for policy, business and IT. CIRPASS Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11127410>

The objective of the study was to identify drivers, barriers, opportunities, challenges, and actionable recommendations for the successful implementation and delivery of DPPs within the scope of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR). The part of the study related to recommendations is not considered here as it is out of the scope of the survey.

Drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges are defined as follows:

- Drivers: Forces or catalysts that guide progress towards a goal or achievement of a desired outcome.
- Barriers: Impediments or obstacles that impede progress towards a goal or achievement of a desired outcome.
- Opportunities: Situations or occasions that offer a chance to undertake a specific action.
- Challenges: Situations or occasions that require considerable effort, skill, and determination to undertake a specific action.

The study considered both general elements for DPPs and elements specific to three sectors: batteries, textiles, and electronics. Specificities of the sectors were pointed out where possible. Nevertheless, due to the early phase of the DPP and the DPP system, few sector-specific characteristics were identified. For this reason, the results of the study were integrated into general statements on drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges.

2.1 METHOD

The CIRPASS study identified and ranked drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges based on desk research of the literature, other CIRPASS activities, four online workshops, and a survey. For the definition of the elements, the following dimensions were considered:

- regulatory and institutional;
- economic and market;
- social and cultural;
- technological and technical infrastructure;
- environmental;
- knowledge and education;
- value chain and physical infrastructure.

The online workshops were conducted between May and June 2023. Each focused on a domain of application of the DPP: cross-sectoral, batteries, textiles, and electronics. The participants in the workshops on cross-sectoral DPPs and electronics (the ones of interest for this document) were 43 and 34, respectively.

The workshops allowed the aggregation and categorisation of drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges.

Based on the results from the workshops, a survey was conducted in November and December 2023 to evaluate the relevance and awareness of the first list of elements. It was sent to 793 registered CIRPASS stakeholders. In total, 128 responses were received. Although electronics was a relevant sector for the CIRPASS project, the participation from its stakeholders was low (only 15 responses).

2.2 DRIVERS, BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND CHALLENGES

The CIRPASS report detailed 10 drivers, 28 barriers, 32 opportunities, and 30 challenges. The elements were numbered and ranked according to their perceived relevance to the implementation and delivery of DPPs. This ranking was determined by the stakeholders participating in the survey, with D1, B1, O1, and C1 being the driver, barrier, opportunity, and challenge with the highest ranking, and D10, B28, O32, and C30 the one with the lowest ranking. All the elements are reported in the next section, with the new ranking identified by the participants of the survey conducted in 2025.

3 EEE SURVEY: METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

The current survey was conducted from July 17th to September 21st 2025. It focused primarily on the voluntary adoption of DPPs in anticipation of potentially mandatory DPPs through future delegated acts of the ESPR.

3.1 SURVEY DESIGN

The survey consisted of four main parts: drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges. A preliminary part consisted of two main questions aiming to gather information about the role of the company in the EEE value chain and their familiarity with the ESPR.

The survey proposed exactly the same lists of drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges as defined in the CIRPASS study, including the identical ranking of the elements. For each element of the lists, participants were asked to rate their impact on DPP adoption in the EEE sector on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (very low impact) to 5 (very high impact). In addition, for each list, experts were asked whether they identified any additional elements that should be added.

No questions in the survey were mandatory; participants could answer on a voluntary basis and withdraw at any time. Nevertheless, response completeness was very high, with 97.6% of valid responses collected across the survey, indicating a strong level of participant engagement across the four lists. All responses were anonymous.

3.2 RESULTS

28 responses were received to the survey. As seen in Figure 1, the companies of the participants cover different roles in the EEE value chain. ‘Other’ respondents described roles spanning software and digital service provision, testing, inspection and certification services, consulting and advisory services on ESPR/DPP compliance, data centre and high-performance computing operations with hardware reuse, distribution, and the development of advanced technologies for sectors such as automotive electronics, EV batteries, consumer electronics, and ICT. Nearly one third of the ‘Other’ respondents were software service providers.

FIGURE 1: ROLES COVERED BY THE COMPANIES OF THE PARTICIPANTS IN THE EEE SUPPLY CHAIN.

Figure 2 shows the participants' knowledge of the ESPR. Most of them are familiar with the regulation. It should be noted that the respondents, as EWG4 participants, are likely to be more familiar with DPP and ESPR topics than the broader EEE market; the results should therefore be interpreted as reflecting the perspectives of a relatively informed stakeholder group rather than those of the market at large.

FIGURE 2: KNOWLEDGE OF THE ESPR BY THE PARTICIPANTS IN THE SURVEY.

This survey made it possible to revise the ranking of the drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges identified in the first CIRPASS study by considering the specificities of the EEE sector. Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4 present the elements ranked according to this new EEE-specific ranking. To facilitate comparison and clearly highlight changes in priorities, the same nomenclature as in the previous survey has been maintained. For each element, the tables report the average score received, the standard deviation, and the change in ranking compared with the results of the previous survey.

Driver	Average score	Standard deviation	Ranking change
<p>D1 - Regulatory push and pull effects</p> <p><i>New and upcoming regulations around sustainability, such as the ESPR and delegated acts, require the development and implementation of DPPs, creating a regulatory push for eco-innovations.</i></p>	4.57	0.77	—
<p>D9 - High demand for user data</p> <p><i>Firms and e-commerce platforms have a growing interest in customer and product data. DPPs can be helpful in collecting this information.</i></p>	3.61	1.11	↑7
<p>D6 - Informed decisions based on comparison</p> <p><i>For an increasing number of consumers, a product's sustainability significantly influences their purchasing decisions. DPPs could allow for a better assessment of the environmental impact and resource consumption of products, enabling informed decisions based on robust data. For example, the transparency created by DPPs allows comparisons between similar products of different producers.</i></p>	3.57	1.05	↑3

<p>D3 - Rising consumer expectations on transparency</p> <p><i>An increasing number of consumers expect access to the product's sustainability information when making purchasing decisions. The availability of this information could contribute to the acceptance and widespread use of DPPs among the general public.</i></p>	3.57	1.09	↓1
<p>D8 - Increasing pressure on governments due to resource scarcity</p> <p><i>Global supply chains for resources such as rare earth metals have become less reliable. Businesses are increasingly interested in legislative solutions such as the DPP to secure resource flows through improved recycling and other circular strategies.</i></p>	3.53	1.24	↑3
<p>D2 - A growing market for circular and sustainable products</p> <p><i>An emerging market for circular and sustainable products, driven by consumer demand and EU regulations, is increasing the interest in DPPs. Second-hand markets, buy-back and trade-in schemes are becoming more accepted. The scarcity of virgin materials and increased profitability of recycling further promote DPPs.</i></p>	3.46	1.12	↓4
<p>D7 - Expectations of cost savings and economic gains</p> <p><i>Firms expect improved transparency, traceability, and resource and product flows by using DPPs, leading to increased efficiency, cost savings, new revenue streams, higher technology usage, and higher customer demand.</i></p>	3.41	1.53	—
<p>D4 - Existing regulatory incentives for sustainability</p> <p><i>Existing taxation and regulation schemes that target sustainability goals, e.g., the right to repair, can leverage the data stored on DPPs, thereby enhancing their adoption.</i></p>	3.33	1.49	↓4
<p>D5 - Increased awareness about social and environmental problems</p> <p><i>There is growing awareness about child labour issues related to the mining of rare metals, human rights violations in supply chains, and the impacts of waste on the environment and human health. Both the general public and businesses acknowledge the need for solutions such as the DPP to support the transition towards a circular economy.</i></p>	3.21	1.17	↓4
<p>D10 - Existing infrastructure, IT solutions and processes</p> <p><i>In several industries, there are already foundations upon which the circular economy and DPPs can be built. Many products and components are serialised and have digital labels to track them in the value chain. DPP proofs of concepts have been implemented on a smaller scale. There is a high standardisation of parts and</i></p>	3.21	1.34	—

processes. Finally, many IT solutions exist that track and store product data.

TABLE 1: RANKING OF DRIVERS BASED ON THEIR PERCEIVED IMPACT FOR DPP ADOPTION IN EEE SECTOR

Table 1 shows that the driver related to regulation (D1) continues to be rated as having the highest impact on DPP adoption. Another driver rated as having a high impact in the current study (but previously rated as having low impact) is the demand for user data (D9). In addition, several drivers related to sustainability and circularity have decreased in ranking. Finally, the technological and technical infrastructure (D10) is still considered a driver with low impact. However, it should be noted that even the lowest-ranked drivers (D5 and D10) received an average score of 3.21, while in the previous study the lowest-ranked drivers scored 2.86 (D10) and 2.88 (D9). This indicates that they are still perceived as relevant in this study, albeit less influential relative to other factors.

The following other drivers were identified by the participants:

- DPP as foundation for value-added processes: re-connect a brand with its customers.
- Integration of secure and interoperable data exchange infrastructures, leveraging API-first architectures and emerging technologies such as blockchain, to ensure trust, transparency, and compliance-by-design in DPP implementation.
- Enhanced competitiveness thanks to increased traceability and sustainability.

Barrier	Average score	Standard deviation	Ranking change
<p>B3 - Complexity of the value chain</p> <p><i>Multi-tiered and cross-geography value chains face challenges in collecting data for DPPs due to the multitude of actors and partners involved within them. Stakeholders have varied business models and data interests. SMEs might be especially vulnerable in this context. This complexity implies different power relationships among them and difficulties in reaching a consensus on appropriate solutions. For example, dismantlers, shredders, and recyclers in the automotive sector require different end-of-life data.</i></p>	4.53	0.98	↑2
<p>B4 - Missing data from international actors outside the EU</p> <p><i>Numerous industries produce a significant portion of their products or source components and raw materials outside the EU (e.g., batteries from China). It remains unclear to what extent international stakeholders will increase cooperation efforts with EU actors to gather the required data for the DPP.</i></p>	4.39	1.01	↑2
<p>B8 - Unclear financial benefits</p> <p><i>There is a lack of estimations about the financial benefits of implementing DPPs in the medium and long term, thereby hindering a discussion about risks and benefits.</i></p>	4.32	0.96	↑5

<p>B9 - Lack of willingness to provide product data</p> <p><i>Industries characterised by fierce innovation and competition may be reluctant to provide or share product data (e.g., product raw material composition) with third parties. The demand for data transparency clashes with the need to protect intellectual property and maintain a competitive advantage.</i></p>	4.28	0.92	↑5
<p>B5 - Lack of standards</p> <p><i>Standards are crucial to maximise the benefits of DPPs and operationalise a robust and efficient circular economy. In particular, standards are needed for data and IT systems, design and spare parts, or the location of electronic tags. The current lack of standards hinders the widespread adoption of DPPs</i></p>	4.25	1.08	—
<p>B7 - Navigating in a complex regulatory framework</p> <p><i>The large number of national and international regulations create a complex environment, especially for firms with cross-sectoral product portfolios, leading to conflicts between data sharing and data protection activities.</i></p>	4.21	0.86	↑1
<p>B6 - Higher costs and limited financial resources</p> <p><i>Firms may lack the financial resources to establish the necessary IT systems and technological infrastructure (e.g., data carriers) for DPPs. Additional funds for employee training and data management are needed, such as data gathering, tracking, storage, maintenance, and auditing, as well as correcting inaccuracies. SMEs might face constraints due to low IT capabilities and financial resources, potentially transferring higher costs to their customers through price increases.</i></p>	4.07	1.06	↓1
<p>B25 - Changing political landscape</p> <p><i>European elections pose the risk that the DPP deployment is delayed or stopped altogether.</i></p>	4.03	0.86	↑17
<p>B22 - Lack of appropriate ecosystems, business models and infrastructure</p> <p><i>Profitable and established capacities for circularity are crucial. There is potential for improving business models and ecosystems at scale as pilots already exist. However, manual methods are still used for dismantling in recycling settings. Batteries are still evolving, and their raw material composition and construction may change in the future. This lack of scale hinders the adoption of DPPs because of fewer use cases for product data collection, analysis, and exchange.</i></p>	4.03	1.01	↑13

<p>B1 - Lack of awareness about current developments among firms</p> <p><i>Many firms, especially in the supply chain, are unaware of the developments surrounding DPPs and lack an understanding of how they could utilise them for their business. Overall, awareness of the DPP varies widely between countries and industries.</i></p>	4.03	1.11	↓9
<p>B11 - Wide diversity of specifications and standards for single products</p> <p><i>Manufacturers face complexities and low standardisation in their production cycles due to multiple individual products and components, their specifications, and highly volatile assembly lines (i.e., a component used in the same model could be produced by different suppliers). This leads to highly data-intensive and possibly multiple DPPs for a single product. This is particularly relevant for electronics.</i></p>	3.85	1.05	—
<p>B14 - Unclear benefits for the supply chain</p> <p><i>International suppliers are uncertain about how the additional efforts of collecting DPP data could benefit their own business. This lowers their willingness to cooperate and share data.</i></p>	3.82	1.13	↑2
<p>B2 - Lack of expertise and proficiency</p> <p><i>Especially among SMEs and small suppliers, the necessary IT skills to establish a DPP data architecture are missing. Shortfalls in data literacy and technical proficiency in semantic web technologies are common. Digital maturity is often unevenly distributed within supply chains, and substantial knowledge gaps persist between industry, consumers, and regulators.</i></p>	3.75	1.02	↓11
<p>B10 - Loss of traceability during the use phase</p> <p><i>Electronic tags may be lost, removed, or damaged for various reasons, leading to a loss of product traceability. For instance, textiles often lose their QR codes because the labels are cut out by consumers or the printed tags fade with subsequent washing cycles.</i></p>	3.75	1.21	↓4
<p>B24 - High granularity required by regulation</p> <p><i>Equipping low-value products sold in large quantities (e.g., socks) with DPPs may be uneconomical.</i></p>	3.64	1.28	↑9
<p>B23 - Volatile market environment and stressed organisations</p> <p><i>Amid global financial strain and economic difficulties over the past years, a systemic change such as the introduction of DPPs could create resistance among organisations and put acceptance at risk.</i></p>	3.61	1.17	↑7

<p>B15 - Lack of leadership and innovation pathway</p> <p><i>There are uncertainties about what entities within the business and policymaking communities shall take a leadership role in conducting the large-scale deployment of DPPs beyond pilots or small-scale solutions. In addition, the unclear scope and vision of the DPP hinders the emergence of a concrete innovation pathway.</i></p>	3.57	1.23	↓2
<p>B12 - High complexity of the supporting IT architecture</p> <p><i>The complexity and length of data requirements at multiple layers for the DPP might appear overwhelming or incomprehensible and drive away relevant stakeholders.</i></p>	3.5	1.08	↓6
<p>B18 - High manpower costs and labour taxes</p> <p><i>Firms face obstacles in implementing circular strategies due to high manpower costs and labour taxes, particularly in highly manual activities with low automation levels, such as repair, remanufacturing, or recycling.</i></p>	3.5	1.14	↓1
<p>B13 - Diverse digital readiness of the EU member states</p> <p><i>Significant differences in digital readiness among EU member states, related to implementation costs and a lack of digital capabilities, may impede the implementation of DPPs in certain countries.</i></p>	3.5	1.34	↓7
<p>B17 - Diversity of IT systems among firms</p> <p><i>Differences in data architecture and IT systems among companies along the value chain hinder data exchange.</i></p>	3.42	1.32	↓4
<p>B19 - Bypassing compliance controls</p> <p><i>In some industries, it is relatively easy to bypass regulatory requirements by shipping old products to third countries instead of declaring them waste. To effectively introduce DPPs, it will be necessary to eliminate the respective gaps in regulation.</i></p>	3.28	1.22	↓3
<p>B16 - Lack of qualified personnel</p> <p><i>There is a lack of human resources in the EU due to an ageing society. Implementing DPPs requires recruiting qualified experts or training employees, which may cause delays.</i></p>	3.14	1.31	↓7
<p>B20 - Limited consumer access to products using DPPs</p> <p><i>Most DPP initiatives are still in the pilot stage, and consumers have yet to experience them. For example, modern batteries with DPPs are often not available for consumers as a direct purchasing option,</i></p>	3.14	1.3	↓4

<i>such as in the case of electric vehicles and solar photovoltaic storage, where they are embedded in another product.</i>			
<p>B21 - Cultural resistance and path dependency</p> <p><i>Initial implementation difficulties and path dependency on functioning legacy systems could lead to resistance against implementing DPPs. In addition, combining current centralised systems with a decentralised architecture is seen as a burden by firms.</i></p>	2.96	1.23	↓4
<p>B26 - Increasing customer power</p> <p><i>Extensive transparency could catalyse campaigns against controversial business practices and misbehaviour. This increased customer negotiation power could discourage firms from adopting DPPs and higher transparency standards.</i></p>	2.92	1.1	—
<p>B28 - Additional steps in sorting due to electronic data carriers</p> <p><i>Using electronic data carriers could slow down industrial sorting processes and create inefficiencies</i></p>	2.78	0.97	↑1
<p>B27 - Low consumer interest in used goods</p> <p><i>New products still symbolise status, and fashion trends significantly influence consumption patterns. For instance, there is low consumer awareness about WEEE regulations and the significance of returning used products. DPPs may be superfluous if the interest in used products remains low and business models do not shift towards that direction.</i></p>	2.5	0.91	↓1

TABLE 2: BARRIERS RANKING ACCORDING TO THEIR PERCEIVED IMPACT FOR DPP ADOPTION IN EEE SECTOR

Table 2 shows that the barriers perceived with the highest impact for the DPP adoption in the EEE sector are related to the value chain, particularly its complexity (B3) and the potential lack of data on source components and raw materials outside the EU (B4). It is worth noting that, compared to the previous study conducted within CIRPASS, barriers related to knowledge and education (B1 and B2) are no longer considered as the ones with the highest impact. Instead, barriers reflecting a more systemic view in terms of policy (B25) and ecosystems (B22) have gained prominence.

Other barriers identified by the participants are the following:

- Need of a new DPP for modified devices.
- Missing interoperability.
- DPP adoption will depend on the DPP content (granularity level) with significant potential issues related to industrial protection.
- Possible conflicts with existing laws outside the EU.

Opportunity	Average score	Standard deviation	Ranking change
<p>O1 - Providing information on the material composition for recycling</p> <p><i>DPPs could store information about the product's material composition to improve recycling. For instance, in the case of textiles with blended fibres, this information could be used to separate fibres.</i></p>	4.42	1.54	—
<p>O11 - Enabling new business opportunities</p> <p><i>The introduction of DPPs could present numerous business opportunities and use cases. For example, reducing reliance on international raw material suppliers through growing secondary markets or enhancing brand reputation through transparency. Value chains could become more efficient through data transparency, robotic automation, and standardisation. Industries may create better-paying jobs and retain know-how by increasing their products' and operations' sophistication, quality, and sustainability performance.</i></p>	4.19	1.47	↑9
<p>O12 - Scaling up circularity</p> <p><i>By leveraging DPP data, firms could rapidly and effectively scale up already in place individual circular strategies such as maintenance, repair, or recycling, as well as develop an integrated approach to execute several circular strategies in parallel.</i></p>	4.11	1.56	↑9
<p>O15 - Simplifying access to product data in real-time</p> <p><i>Implementing DPPs could provide easy access to product and process data for end consumers and businesses. For example, digital product wallets or exchanges on electronic devices (e.g., smartphones) could further simplify access for all users, including individuals with disabilities, and showcase the product's environmental impact.</i></p>	4.08	1.39	↑11
<p>O2 - Increasing recovery and use of recycled materials</p> <p><i>DPPs and related technologies could facilitate material recovery at the product's end of life, thus helping to scale up recycling, increasing the quality and availability of recyclates, and supporting collection and sorting schemes.</i></p>	4.08	1.52	↓3
<p>O10 - Utilising standards for smooth DPP implementation</p> <p><i>Implementing EU-wide standards and guidelines could drive the introduction of DPPs, offering companies clarity on expectations</i></p>	3.96	1.46	↑4

<i>and obligations placed on them. This, in turn, may help them reduce implementation costs.</i>			
<p>O4 - Simplifying maintenance and repair</p> <p><i>Product data stored on DPPs could provide details on required spare parts, offer disassembly and repair instructions, and help users identify already repaired or replaced parts. Thus, regular users could undertake minor repairs themselves while more complex activities could be handled by established operators, thereby boosting the efficiency of circular maintenance and repair.</i></p>	3.96	1.54	↓3
<p>O5 - Providing sorters and recyclers with valuable insights</p> <p><i>The information provided by DPPs could allow sorters and recyclers to increase their process efficiency by planning recycling methods in advance according to the product and material types.</i></p>	3.96	1.54	↓3
<p>O14 - Facilitating take-back of used products</p> <p><i>DPPs could enhance takeback and buy-back options for used products. This aids in closing circular economy loops by providing location and condition information, as demonstrated in successful attempts to implement this approach with less technological support, especially in the textile industry (e.g., carpets).</i></p>	3.92	1.49	↑5
<p>O7 - Limiting greenwashing and plagiarism</p> <p><i>Standardised data collection and product data disclosure could mitigate greenwashing and plagiarism risks. Transparent information may support certification, allowing civil society, authorities, or third-party auditors to verify compliance. Intellectual property information could also be included in the DPP and be easily verified when buying a product.</i></p>	3.85	1.49	↓3
<p>O3 - Increasing economic benefits from sustainable products</p> <p><i>Firms could leverage the transparency generated by DPPs to showcase certifications and sustainable product standards, e.g., energy labels and repair scores, increasing their economic benefit and competitive advantage.</i></p>	3.85	1.61	↓8
<p>O6 - Improving product design based on data</p> <p><i>Access to in-depth usage and end-of-life data allows firms to optimise product development and design for circularity, addressing customer demand for increased sustainability. Product data stored on DPPs could incentivise firms to prioritise quality and reliability over quantity, potentially bringing systemic change and fostering innovative, sustainable ideas in product design.</i></p>	3.81	1.42	↓6

<p>O8 - Reducing waste and improving resource efficiency</p> <p><i>DPP data could help prevent resource losses, minimise waste generation, and reduce raw material extraction by enabling longer product lifetimes and more efficient production and take-back processes.</i></p>	3.81	1.45	↓5
<p>O16 - Shifting towards service business models</p> <p><i>DPPs could drive the shift towards service business models such as rentals or leasing by enabling continuous product monitoring and take-back. Consumers could benefit from durable, high-quality products and access to maintenance, repair, or replacement (e.g., in case of relocation) services. Servitisation could also help firms attract younger user demographics to their customer base.</i></p>	3.81	1.47	↑2
<p>O25 - Gaining insights and knowledge</p> <p><i>DPP data could aid firms in generating market knowledge and streamlining procurement by offering them insights into supply chain providers, their products, know-how and performance. Access to product data could allow firms to analyse consumer behaviour for educational or economic purposes.</i></p>	3.73	1.45	↑10
<p>O22 - Integrating several regulations</p> <p><i>The ESPR could serve as a foundation to consolidate other regulatory initiatives under one framework, simplifying reporting for companies. This could save firms time and effort in the long term. In addition, firms could use DPPs to integrate reporting on various sustainability regulations under one platform.</i></p>	3.69	1.57	↑6
<p>O9 - Creating an interoperable infrastructure for data exchange</p> <p><i>Creating an interoperable and automated data architecture that is easily accessible could create numerous opportunities for future business and use cases. Firms could profit from a data-centred culture and use the DPP as a single source of environmental (and other product-related) information.</i></p>	3.65	1.39	↓8
<p>O24 - Calculating demand and supply for recyclates</p> <p><i>Analysing DPP data could allow multiple stakeholders to collaborate in estimating future demand and supply for recyclates. Firms and recyclers could leverage this information to establish long-term cooperation and supply contracts.</i></p>	3.57	1.41	↑6
<p>O13 - Educating the customer about sustainability impacts</p> <p><i>DPPs could empower consumers to understand the environmental impact of their products. NGOs and firms could use the DPP as a</i></p>	3.57	1.49	↓6

<p><i>channel to educate consumers about the footprint of their goods. This could counteract harmful trends like fast fashion and spread knowledge about sustainable behaviour.</i></p>			
<p>O18 - Tracking and enforcing regulations and standards</p> <p><i>DPP data and related transparency could allow authorities to verify firms' compliance with regulations. Firms, in turn, could ensure adherence to standards among their supplier base. Authorities could take regulatory actions, such as bans or increased taxes, for products not meeting sustainability or ethical criteria. Overall, this could enhance market surveillance and enable firms to respond more effectively to supply chain disruptions.</i></p>	3.57	1.51	↓2
<p>O17 - Becoming a leader in environmental regulation</p> <p><i>The EU could become a role model in environmental regulation for other parts of the world, especially the global south, by adopting pioneering rules and standards. In addition, regulation on DPPs could be a gateway for further European regulation to expand standards on a global scale.</i></p>	3.53	1.55	↓4
<p>O28 - Learning from past initiatives</p> <p><i>To successfully scale up sustainability regulations such as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation to a global level, lessons could be drawn from previous international regulatory and standardisation efforts.</i></p>	3.46	1.39	↑6
<p>O21 - Promoting cultural change towards circularity and sustainability</p> <p><i>Implementing DPPs could enable consumers to align purchasing decisions with sustainability, fostering a potential shift away from the "throwaway society". For instance, consumers could learn about the environmental impact of electronic products, raise their demand for second-hand products, or become temporary users instead of owners under service business models.</i></p>	3.42	1.65	↓2
<p>O19 - Preventing and exposing environmental, social and governance (ESG) violations</p> <p><i>With higher data transparency, firms engaged in questionable or harmful business practices related to ESG criteria could be more easily exposed. The pressure created by higher transparency could lead to a general decrease in such practices.</i></p>	3.34	1.45	↓5
<p>O29 - Promoting knowledge exchange and cooperation</p> <p><i>The increased networking of actors along the value chain due to data exchange could promote cooperation and knowledge transfer</i></p>	3.32	1.55	↑4

<i>among them. This could lead to the rapid spreading of sustainability know-how and best practices.</i>			
<p>O26 - Informing policymaking</p> <p><i>The data transparency generated by DPP could provide valuable insights for formulating new policies or adjusting existing ones. Policymakers could assess the implementation of the circular economy and derive policies based on data.</i></p>	3.31	1.49	—
<p>O32 - Monetising product data</p> <p><i>DPP data could be monetised, for instance, through a premium access model. This could generate additional revenue for firms and the emergence of new markets based on data exchange.</i></p>	3.26	1.35	↑5
<p>O30 - Streamlining process capabilities</p> <p><i>An automated data architecture spanning the manufacturing cycle and the entire value chain could enable business process optimisation. Firms could generate reports and conduct mandatory control checks in a timely manner. As robust data is available, payments and other administrative processes could also be streamlined.</i></p>	3.23	1.39	↑2
<p>O20 - Building on existing technologies and ecosystems</p> <p><i>Leveraging existing technological solutions (e.g., data carriers) and industry ecosystems could simplify the implementation of DPPs. For instance, established data exchange systems, as seen in industries like automotive, provide a solid foundation for further development.</i></p>	3.19	1.52	↓9
<p>O23 - Reducing costs with automated data exchange</p> <p><i>Using automated data exchange with DPPs along the value chain could significantly reduce costs. For instance, real-time monitoring systems and digital data carriers could enable data sharing with multiple customers or the automation of reporting and auditing tasks.</i></p>	3.08	1.64	↓7
<p>O27 - Benefiting from decentralised data architecture</p> <p><i>A decentralised data architecture for DPPs could help firms maintain control over their data. This could positively impact the acceptance and willingness to invest in IT systems and computing power for DPPs.</i></p>	3	1.37	↓4
<p>O31 - Regionalising the value chain</p> <p><i>DPP-enabled transparency and traceability of used products could increase the proximity between local and regional producers,</i></p>	3	1.45	↓1

suppliers, and recyclers, thus enabling actors to compete and access domestic value chains.

TABLE 3: RANKING OF OPPORTUNITIES ACCORDING TO THEIR PERCEIVED IMPACT FOR DPP ADOPTION IN THE EEE SECTOR

Table 3 shows that providing information on the material composition for recycling (O1) is still perceived as the opportunity with the highest relevance for the EEE sector. Other opportunities related to economy and markets have gained in perceived impact, particularly enabling new business opportunities (O11) and scaling up circularity (O12). In addition, the opportunity to simplify access to product data in real-time (O15) has gained in perceived impact. On the other hand, regionalising the value chain, by increasing the proximity between local and regional producers, suppliers, and recyclers (O31), is still considered of relatively low relevance.

Other opportunities identified by the participants are the following:

- Increasing awareness on product durability.
- Building up national stocks with resources embedded in devices.
- Increasing worldwide logistic flows at customs due to DPP products automatised data which would lead to efficient custom borders controls reducing fakes and unwanted merchandise.
- Driving business innovation: enabling servitisation, reducing greenwashing, and leveraging secure interoperability for new circular business models.

Challenge	Average score	Standard deviation	Ranking change
<p>C4 - Ensuring data quality</p> <p><i>Automated procedures are essential for auditing the quality of DPP information, especially considering the large number of actors in the value chain and possible duplicates. A gradual implementation of the DPP shall ensure compliance with current standards and regulations (e.g., REACH regulation and SCIP database).</i></p>	4.52	1.17	↑3
<p>C2 - Lacking trustworthy data and dependence on other value chain actors</p> <p><i>Collecting appropriate data for the DPP along the value chain is challenging. There may be a lack of trust in the data provided and a lack of capabilities for accurate data collection among suppliers.</i></p>	4.43	1.01	—
<p>C3 - Aligning relevant regulations with non-European governments</p> <p><i>EU regulations need to be aligned with those of third countries due to the international nature of value and supply chains. Otherwise, foreign data privacy regulations could prohibit the exchange of data for DPPs. Currently, it's unclear how efficient cross-border collaboration will be established to harmonise data governance.</i></p>	4.36	1.14	—

<p>C1 - Ensuring security protocols and data protection</p> <p><i>Sharing product information could lead to unauthorised use of intellectual property (IP) rights, counterfeit, or hacking issues. Security and privacy protocols need to be implemented to prevent such misuse.</i></p>	4.28	1.03	↓3
<p>C7 - Lacking standardisation and guidance by the EU Commission and member states</p> <p><i>Without clear guidelines, standards, and support from the EU Commission and member states, regulation could negatively impact genuine transformation. Firms might prioritise meeting legal obligations and compliance over achieving higher sustainability and circularity.</i></p>	4.25	0.95	↑3
<p>C12 - Changing internal processes, business models and collaboration practices</p> <p><i>Silo-thinking and cultural inertia could hinder the necessary collaboration, practices, and network structures (e.g., across companies, industries, and supply chains) to build efficient circular business models and ecosystems for DPPs.</i></p>	4.14	0.95	↑6
<p>C10 - Missing information about materials</p> <p><i>Companies might not have clarity about the materials used in their products and what data should be collected about them in the DPP.</i></p>	4.11	1.01	↑3
<p>C27 - Tight regulatory schedule</p> <p><i>The time pressure for the transition to DPPs poses significant challenges for firms, with some perceiving the transition period as too short.</i></p>	4.11	1.01	↑19
<p>C14 - Measuring environmental impact and footprint</p> <p><i>There is a lack of frameworks to consistently and comparably assess the product's environmental impact. This is also due to different perspectives on sustainability. As a result, capturing appropriate information through DPPs could be challenging.</i></p>	4	1.10	↑5
<p>C6 - Achieving interoperability between data models and IT systems</p> <p><i>To facilitate global and interoperable DPPs, it's crucial to establish overarching data models, ontologies, and technology standards, which are currently missing. For example, integrating the DPP with existing product tracking systems could be difficult without well-established interoperability.</i></p>	4	1.25	↓4

<p>C24 - Scaling up service business models</p> <p><i>Service business models remain rare and challenging to implement. This is particularly difficult for component manufacturers, OEMs, and SMEs due to financial constraints related to long-term capital requirements or value chain dependencies (e.g., leasing car batteries when the car is sold). Due to these challenges, DPPs might not automatically contribute to higher servitisation and resource savings.</i></p>	3.93	1.09	↑13
<p>C20 - Lacking value chain infrastructure for a circular economy</p> <p><i>The lack of a comprehensive value chain infrastructure hinders the adoption of a circular economy at a large scale. Issues include low spare parts production, inadequate disposal practices, insufficient collection points for take-back, low industrialisation of circular activities, and unequal infrastructure within the EU. Building up an effective circular economy requires investments in physical infrastructure, potentially delaying DPP implementation or rendering them unsuitable for some circular use cases.</i></p>	3.93	1.16	↑8
<p>C16 - Building capacity outside the EU</p> <p><i>Europe's leading role in deploying DPPs pressures various governmental and non-governmental stakeholders outside the EU to collaborate and build capacity for DPP deployment. The coordination of such initiatives and the role of the EU in this context remain unclear.</i></p>	3.89	1.23	↑3
<p>C22 - Integrating multiple stakeholders</p> <p><i>Currently, there is a strong focus on implementing the DPP for car batteries. This needs to be expanded to the whole battery industry. Narrow perspectives like these should be avoided from the outset for other product categories, such as textiles and electronics.</i></p>	3.86	1.02	↑8
<p>C5 - Creating a level playing field</p> <p><i>Due to the high IT requirements and investment costs, DPPs could favour a few large companies at the expense of most small businesses, thus contributing to market imbalances. Clear definitions, rules, and requirements for participation based on a level playing field are needed for the DPP system.</i></p>	3.86	1.16	↓10
<p>C25 - Extending firm accountability and liability</p> <p><i>Upcoming regulations may extend the accountability and liability of producing firms beyond the product's sale. This poses challenges for component suppliers such as car battery manufacturers as it remains unclear how they can take back their products after a transfer of ownership of the car.</i></p>	3.81	1.13	↑9

<p>C21 - Recycling is not always sustainable</p> <p><i>The DPP may overemphasise recycling, which can be energy-intensive. Thus, the deployment of the DPP shall focus on all circular strategies for promoting sustainable business practices.</i></p>	3.78	1.01	↑4
<p>C17 - Lacking clarity on data usage by regulators</p> <p><i>It is unclear how and whether regulators can utilise DPP data to work on standardisations or to conduct checks on companies, as these checks are primarily based on self-reporting.</i></p>	3.75	1.12	↓1
<p>C28 - Lock-in issues with service providers</p> <p><i>Firms facing challenges in collecting and organising the extensive data required for DPPs may turn to external IT service suppliers, resulting in power imbalances due to lock-in issues.</i></p>	3.74	1.11	↑9
<p>C8 - Identifying data points</p> <p><i>To advance circularity and share product data through DPPs with ecosystem actors, the relevant data points, such as technical specifications or material composition, need to be identified and agreed upon for each product model and category.</i></p>	3.74	1.37	↓12
<p>C23 - Establishing circular product design</p> <p><i>The deployment of DPPs may not inherently contribute to sustainability or the circular economy, as these outcomes depend on product design considerations. For example, reducing glued connections in a product could enable better recycling, but this and other properties, such as repairability, are independent of DPPs.</i></p>	3.68	1	↑2
<p>C19 - Establishing a suitable data architecture</p> <p><i>The amount of data required for DPPs makes creating systems that automate data management and storage necessary. The architecture for the DPP needs to evolve, follow the changes to the product over time, and allow permanent exchange between companies. It is unclear whether decentralised or centralised data storage and management is better suited for this.</i></p>	3.64	1.29	↓3
<p>C15 - Aligning internal departments</p> <p><i>Additional data requirements for the DPP involve aligning several departments at the firm level, such as CSR, procurement, marketing, IT, and finance. In companies, this alignment is often very low or, in some cases, non-existent.</i></p>	3.53	1.24	↓8
<p>C26 – Increasing energy costs and footprint to scale up IT</p>	3.53	1.24	↑2

<i>Significant energy resources may be needed to store and manage the data to scale up DPPs. Energy calculations should be undertaken and incorporated into the planning process as early as possible to reduce the carbon footprint of the DPPs.</i>			
<p>C11 - Satisfying users' information requirements</p> <p><i>Attractiveness and ease of use are relevant factors to consider in the deployment of DPPs for the general public. Therefore, a balance between sufficient information density and easy comprehension must be ensured. DPP data must not be too superficial, as this would not provide any real added value compared to current labels and certifications.</i></p>	3.46	1.21	↓14
<p>C9 - Educating consumers about relevant concepts</p> <p><i>DPP-related concepts and tools need to be explained to consumers to increase their awareness about DPPs.</i></p>	3.42	1.37	↓17
<p>C29 - Including non-mandatory data by the civil society</p> <p><i>Consumers, NGOs, and civil society institutions may request the addition and generation of data on specific DPPs. However, their role and the extent to which they may add data to a DPP are not yet well defined.</i></p>	3.36	1.23	↑2
<p>C13 - Ensuring user identification and authentication</p> <p><i>Authenticating different stakeholders may pose organisational, technical, and financial challenges. In particular, civil society actors may need access to specific information to monitor and verify the DPP data or may deny access to their private data.</i></p>	3.36	1.26	↓15
<p>C18 - Including multiple languages</p> <p><i>The DPP must be accessible and usable in multiple languages for widespread acceptance.</i></p>	3.14	1.53	↓9
<p>C30 - Increasing electronic waste</p> <p><i>Due to regulatory changes and the introduction of DPPs, the necessary electronic tags, such as QR codes or RFID chips, may increase the amount of electronic and plastic waste.</i></p>	3.03	1.35	—

TABLE 4: RANKING OF CHALLENGES ACCORDING TO THEIR PERCEIVED IMPACT FOR DPP ADOPTION IN THE EEE SECTOR

Table 4 shows that the challenges identified as having the highest impact remain relatively stable. They include challenges related to collecting appropriate data for the DPP along the value chain (C4) and establishing efficient cross-border collaboration (C2). It is worth noting that the challenge related to the time pressure in the transition to DPPs (C27) has increased in perceived impact, while the challenge about

consumer education (C9) has declined considerably in the ranking compared to the previous study (a reduction of 17 places).

Other challenges identified by the participants are the following:

- The regulatory framework is fragmented, and suppliers outside the EU show insufficient awareness, capacity, and transparency.
- Ensuring global interoperability and data quality across multi-tier supply chains.
- Added complexity and government oversight that contributes negatively to the EU economy.

4 ADDITIONAL FEEDBACK FROM EWG4

Following the completion of the EEE survey, additional feedback was received from expert stakeholders of the electronics working group. This feedback supports the survey's findings while providing further clarification on practical implementation priorities, opportunities and challenges for the DPP in the EEE sector.

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION PRIORITIES AND NEEDS

- Need for pragmatic, incremental implementation pathways, particularly for SMEs.

While awareness of DPP requirements is clearly increasing, practical readiness remains limited. Many organisations, especially SMEs, still lack the internal resources, data structures, and operational guidance needed to move from high-level obligations to concrete action. The feedback reinforces the idea that the primary challenges are not conceptual or regulatory, but implementation-related. As a result, many companies perceive the DPP as a distant, long-term requirement rather than an actionable process. To bridge this gap, stakeholders emphasise the value of step-by-step guidance, minimal DPP readiness scenarios, lightweight assessment tools, and targeted pilot projects. Such measures can lower entry barriers, support learning by doing, and help align regulatory expectations with operational realities, thereby accelerating DPP adoption across the EEE sector. In addition, a pragmatic pathway could help companies address structural barriers of the implementation (B3 - Complexity of the value chain and B6 - Higher costs and limited financial resources).

- Full Material Declaration (FMD) as mandatory, accurate, and auditable.

The FMD is viewed as a foundational requirement for enabling regulatory compliance, high-quality recycling, and credible circular economy outcomes. However, stakeholders emphasise that the primary purpose of the FMD is to ensure the existence and reliability of material knowledge within the value chain, rather than to promote unconditional transparency. Without robust and verifiable material declarations, the DPP risks remaining a descriptive tool rather than becoming an operational enabler for sustainability and resource efficiency. The FMD is also implicitly linked to several identified opportunities, as it provides data for recycling and circular activities (O1 - Providing information on the material composition for recycling, O2 – Increasing recovery and use of recycled materials, and O5 – Providing sorters and recyclers with valuable insights).

- DPP and data access: tiered, purpose-bound, and governed.

Reluctance to share data stems from legitimate concerns related to intellectual property, cybersecurity, and competitive exposure, rather than resistance to sustainability objectives. A multi-level DPP model with purpose-limited access, role-based permissions and strong governance mechanisms, combined with clear distinctions between data types, can reduce confidentiality concerns and accelerate adoption. For instance, differentiating between basic mandatory data, operational circularity data, and advanced or voluntary data layers, as well as distinguishing between data declaration and disclosure, can strengthen trust and safeguard sensitive business information. This approach is particularly important for managing dependencies on non-EU suppliers and enabling scalable implementation across complex, multi-tier supply chains. A tiered governance proposal could address diverse identified barriers related to data sharing and IT systems (B9 - Lack of willingness to provide product data, B12 - High complexity of the supporting IT architecture, and B17 - Diversity of IT systems among firms).

- There is a need for continuous corporate DPP training.

The feedback highlights the importance of enhancing corporate training on DPP requirements, not only within EU-based organisations but also across non-EU suppliers integrated into EU value chains. This includes employee training on DPP-related skills to strengthen data modelling capabilities and ensure the security of data transmission. This need is also related to barriers highlighted in the previous survey

(B1 - Lack of awareness about current developments among firms, B2 - Lack of expertise and proficiency, and B16 - Lack of qualified personnel). Although these barriers have decreased in prominence compared to the previous survey (B1: 9 positions, B2: 11 positions, and B16: 7 positions), they remain relevant for achieving implementation objectives.

4.2 OPPORTUNITIES

- Serviceability and repairability represent immediate, high-value opportunities for electronics.

Especially for products such as computers, where modular design and established repair practices already exist, DPP-enabled access to repair instructions, spare-part information, and service status can deliver tangible circular economy benefits with relatively low implementation risk. Prioritising these use cases is seen as a practical way to demonstrate the value of the DPP at an early stage, while aligning closely with EU policy objectives on the right to repair, product lifetime extension, and waste prevention. Although these opportunities were identified in the previous survey (e.g., O12 - Scaling up circularity and O16 - Shifting towards service business models), they are particularly relevant and actionable within the EEE industry.

- DPP can be seen as a feedback loop for innovation.

The DPP can function as a structured mechanism for collecting first-party data on real-world product use and performance. Such data can directly inform engineering decisions, support marketing by anticipating evolving customer needs, and strengthen procurement. In this way, the DPP can actively contribute to continuous improvement and innovation. Similar to the previous point, these opportunities were identified in the previous survey within the broader context of the DPP and also apply to the EEE industry (O25 - Gaining insights and knowledge and O6 - Improving product design based on data).

4.3 CHALLENGES AND RISKS

- EU and non-EU stakeholders can encounter data-sharing challenges.

A critical challenge concerns data-sharing limitations between EU and non-EU stakeholders, especially when non-EU manufacturers rely on upstream components sourced from third-country suppliers. In many cases, non-EU producers are required to provide DPP-relevant lifecycle data for products entering the EU market. However, they lack contractual, legal, or commercial leverage to obtain detailed material or origin data from upstream component manufacturers. This asymmetry creates compliance risks for importers and may unintentionally disrupt global supply chains. The feedback underlines the need for the EU-DPP governance to recognise these structural constraints and support pragmatic mechanisms such as tiered data requirements, standardised data request templates, and secure data bridge solutions that protect intellectual property while enabling regulatory alignment. This issue was also identified in the previous survey under both barriers and challenges (B4 - Missing data from international actors outside the EU, B9 - Lack of willingness to provide product data, and C2 - Lacking trustworthy data and dependence on other value chain actors).

- There is a risk of knowledge and interpretation gaps between EU and non-EU organisations.

The feedback highlights significant differences in DPP awareness and interpretation between EU and non-EU organisations, driven by linguistic barriers and differing legal and cultural frameworks. As the DPP and ESPR originate within the EU regulatory context, non-EU companies, particularly SMEs, may struggle to translate high-level EU requirements into operational practices. This risk has been partially identified in the previous survey in the context of collaboration challenges among international stakeholders (C16 - Building capacity outside the EU).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Understanding drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges related to the adoption of the DPP in the EEE sector is essential for both policymakers and businesses. Such insights support the legislative process and facilitate the development of the DPP across the value chain. Building on the previous study conducted within the CIRPASS project, the survey described in this document presents how the perceived impact of various drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges has evolved two years after the initial study, with a specific focus on EEE. While some elements remain stable, others vary significantly in their perceived relevance.

The survey participants represent different roles across the EEE value chain and exhibit strong knowledge and awareness of the ESPR. In addition to answering the quantitative section of the survey, participants have proposed qualitative insights into drivers, barriers, opportunities, and challenges to enrich the findings of the survey. Furthermore, additional feedback from expert stakeholders of the electronics working group has been collected to complement the survey.

The following key findings can be highlighted from the survey:

- **Drivers:** Three main conclusions can be drawn from the results of the survey. First, regulatory requirements remain the main driver of DPP adoption. This suggests that the EEE industry continues to place emphasis on compliance. Second, demand for user data has increased substantially in perceived importance for the EEE sector. This can be explained by the sector's strong interest in customer and product data, and the fact that DPPs can help collect this information. However, the survey did not explicitly distinguish between different types of user data. Future studies could differentiate these categories and examine their respective implications for governance, security, and cross-border data management. Finally, issues related to resource scarcity have gained importance, while environmental concerns have decreased in significance. These findings reflect wider societal trends related to current economic and political developments. This shift may be partially attributed to differences in respondent composition, as fewer circular economy actors participated in the current survey.
- **Barriers:** Issues related to data collection and transfer have gained in importance. This suggests that companies are beginning to assess their data needs and may be encountering concrete challenges in collecting and managing information for the DPP. In addition, the lack of awareness about current developments among firms and the lack of expertise and proficiency, which were rated as top barriers in the previous study, are now perceived as having a lower impact. This may indicate increased awareness of developments surrounding the DPP and stronger expertise acquired in recent years. However, it may also reflect the specific profile of the survey participants, who are likely to be more informed and actively engaged with the DPP and ESPR, rather than a structural change across the EEE sector.
- **Opportunities:** The follow-up survey indicates a clear shift in perceived high-impact opportunities. Respondents now consistently rank enabling new business opportunities and scaling up circularity as the most impactful. These findings may suggest a maturation in how stakeholders in the EEE sector perceive the DPP, viewing it as a strategic enabler for both business development and the circular economy. Similarly to the identified drivers, this shift may be explained by companies aiming to achieve greater resource independence in response to geopolitical risks and supply chain vulnerabilities, which could be addressed by circular value chains.
- **Challenges:** The survey highlights that data quality and trustworthiness, cross-border alignment, and security are the most significant challenges. Addressing them will require concrete implementation measures, such as clear regulatory guidance, robust governance models with roles and responsibilities, and practical mechanisms for data verification and auditing. While these core challenges remain stable compared to the previous survey, others have increased sharply in perceived importance, particularly those related to tight regulatory timelines and the scaling up of service business models. In contrast, educating consumers about relevant concepts has dropped significantly in perceived importance. Overall, these developments highlight a transition from

conceptual and awareness-related challenges toward execution-oriented constraints, reinforcing the need for regulatory guidance and scalable operational models to support effective DPP adoption.

The additional expert feedback also suggests a shift from conceptual concerns to operational and governance-related aspects of the DPP implementation. Assessment tools, pilot projects and clear guidance are essential for practical readiness. In addition, data governance emerges as a central success factor for the effectiveness and acceptance of the DPP. Furthermore, capacity-building remains necessary to ensure onboarding of global value chains. Finally, the DPP presents concrete innovation opportunities, particularly in enhancing serviceability and reparability of EEE.

Overall, ensuring effective adoption of the DPP will depend on operational clarity, scalable governance mechanisms, and international alignment.